

D4.1 COMMUNITY BUILDING & COMMUNICATION STRATEGY AND PLAN

Revision: v.1.0

Work package	WP4
Task	Task 4.1
Due date	31/03/2024
Submission date	04/04/2024
Deliverable lead	Martel GmbH (MAR)
Version	1.0
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Abstract	The document presents the communication and dissemination goals of the NGI Commons project, its operational context and overall ambition, the target audiences, as well as main planned activities to help promote the overall project's work and outcomes. The document also described the impact creation tools and actions, as well as a monitoring framework developed to help execute the strategy, to help measure its impact, and conduct the most accurate assessment of its overall effectiveness.
Keywords	Community building, communication, dissemination, stakeholders' engagement, impact creation, NGI, digital/internet commons.

Document Revision History

Version	Date	Description of change	List of contributor(s)
V0.1	27/02/2024	1st version shared with the consortium	Klaudia dos Santos (MAR)
V0.2	20/03/2024	Incorporation of input provided by the consortium; 2nd version shared with internal reviewers	Klaudia dos Santos, Margherita Facca (MAR)
V0.3	27/03/2024	Internal review completed	Nicholas Gates (OFE)
V0.4	28/03/2024	Final revision by the deliverable lead	Valentin Popescu (MAR)
V0.5	29/03/2024	Final formatting and polish	Margherita Facca (MAR)
V1.0	02/04/2024	Submission	Eugenia Kyriotis (MIN)

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Project funded by

Schweizerische Eidgenossenschaft
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Federal Department of Economic Affairs,
Education and Research EAER
State Secretariat for Education,
Research and Innovation SERI

NGI Commons (*Open Source and Internet Commons for Europe's Digital Sovereignty*) project is funded by the European Union's [Horizon Europe research and innovation programme](#) under Grant Agreement number 101135279. This work has received funding from the [Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research, and Innovation \(SERI\)](#).

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* R: Document, report (excluding the periodic and final reports)

DEM: Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs

DEC: Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc.

DATA: Data sets, microdata, etc.

DMP: Data management plan

ETHICS: Deliverables related to ethics issues.

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OTHER: Software, technical diagram, algorithms, models, etc.

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The "**D4.1 Community Building & Communication Strategy and Plan**" document outlines the strategic approach for communication, dissemination and community engagement for NGI Commons CSA. This strategy is designed to maximise the project's impact, ensuring the achievement of its communication objectives and fostering a vibrant, inclusive framework that engages all target groups across Europe and beyond.

NGI Commons is positioned at the intersection of digital innovation and community engagement, with a focus on promoting digital/internet commons (DC/IC), open-source initiatives, and ensuring a cohesive approach to European digital sovereignty efforts.

This strategy document provides a detailed blueprint of the project's ambitions, target audiences, communication goals, and the planned activities to achieve these goals.

A key component of this strategy is the identification and engagement of diverse stakeholder groups, including the digital/internet commons community, open-source community, extended NGI community, policymakers, researchers, and the general public. By leveraging a multi-channel communication approach, the project aims to communicate its objectives, work, and results effectively, promote relevant DC/IC initiatives, and foster synergies across local, national, and possibly global efforts.

The strategy emphasises the importance of internal communication within the consortium, impact creation through various phases, and community building through direct engagement and liaisons with key organisations and initiatives. It details specific tools and activities such as the development of a visual identity, project website, social media engagement, promotional materials, and participation in and organisation of events. Furthermore, it outlines a comprehensive impact assessment framework to measure the effectiveness of the strategy, including key performance indicators and a communication matrix to track progress and outcomes.

The "D4.1 Community Building & Communication Strategy and Plan" serves as a foundational document for NGI Commons, guiding its efforts to build a robust, engaged community around the principles of digital commons and open-source innovation. Through strategic communication and dissemination efforts, the project seeks to amplify its impact, contribute to the shaping of European digital policy, and ultimately, support the development of a more inclusive, democratic, and sovereign digital landscape in Europe.

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ABBREVIATIONS

DC	Digital Commons
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
IC	Internet Commons
KPIs	Key Performance Indicators
M	Month
NGI	Next Generation Internet
OS	Open Source
WP	Work Package

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 PURPOSE OF THE DOCUMENT

This deliverable, prepared in the context of WP4 (Outreach and Impact), defines the communication, dissemination, and community building strategy and describes the activities NGI Commons will pursue to guarantee the project's broad visibility, its adequate promotion, and uptake of its results. The strategy provides a framework for different outreach activities that will be carried out throughout the project by the project consortium with the ambition of achieving the following objectives:

- create a vibrant and disruptive framework engaging all target groups in Europe and beyond,
- communicate the project's objectives, work, and results through a rich set of tools and actions,
- promote relevant digital/internet commons (DC/IC) initiatives, engaging them in the NGI,
- promote the NGI initiative and its values, work, solutions, and funding to grow DC/IC efforts,
- communicate and increase awareness of European digital sovereignty policy-driven efforts, and
- foster synergies and collaboration across relevant local, national, European (and possibly global) efforts.

In addition to setting the communication framework, the strategy provides clear directions for the consortium and can be viewed as a guiding document for project partners, so that they can better align on the communication objectives and planned dissemination activities.

The strategy will be periodically evaluated. Major updates will be included in periodic reports.

1.2 STRUCTURE OF THE DOCUMENT

The sections of this deliverable are organised in the following manner:

- Section 1 provides insights into the project's operational context, shedding light on its main ambition and objectives.
- Section 2 outlines the core aspects of the project's communication, dissemination, and community building strategy and describes planned activities and tools in more detail.
- Section 3 presents the indicators that will be used to assess the effectiveness of the project's impact creation strategy.
- Section 4 concludes the document.

1.3 CONTEXT AND AMBITION

Over the last few decades, digital/internet commons (DC/IC) have become essential components supporting sovereignty, trust, democratic values, and fundamental digital rights and principles, such as privacy and data protection, open knowledge and participation, user control over personal data, decentralisation, inclusiveness, and a green transition, among others. Their economic and geopolitical importance has been growing exponentially, gathering

increasing momentum across several communities, in line with the Digital Decade principles. However, although DC/IC are critical in our digital life, their importance is not fully reflected at the strategic level with little representation of the communities involved, lack of structure, gaps between grassroots commoners and top-down sovereignty policies, and a fragmented funding landscape.

The NGI Commons project was established as a response to the above-mentioned points. Its main ambition is to help the Next Generation Internet (NGI) initiative integrate and align with DC/IC policies at national and European levels. The project also seeks to elaborate a long-term strategy for DC/IC based on a clear mapping of existing communities of commoners and commons, considering top-down policy priorities (e.g., reuse of commons, avoiding overlaps). Finally, the project intends to create a more coherent funding landscape integrating national and European dimensions from public and private sectors.

2 IMPACT CREATION STRATEGY

2.1 INTERNAL COMMUNICATION

Effective internal communication and efficient information flow are a crucial part of any project's operational process. Aware of that, the NGI Commons project implemented several tools and activities to ensure a smooth and effective exchange of information among project partners:

- **Mailing list** – to facilitate the communication among the consortium members and keep all partners in the loop, a project mailing list (managed by MIN) was created for general project communication.
- **Repository** – to facilitate the information flow among consortium members and foster effective and successful collaboration among them, a private, password-protected area was established on Google Drive. This repository serves as a library and stores all relevant documents, distribution lists, and information about project-related meetings. It also enables the generation of highlights, presentation of management data (manpower, finances, deliverables, partner contacts, GANTT charts, etc.), and the organisation of meetings. The repository is managed by MIN, which has a corporate subscription to Google services, which ensures an increased level of encryption, and therefore, privacy and data protection.
- **Periodic calls and face-to-face meetings** – the NGI Commons consortium will hold a bimonthly call to discuss the ongoing work, align on the distribution of workload and plan ahead. In person meetings will be held twice a year. If needed, additional ad hoc meetings will be organised to tackle any unforeseen tasks.

2.2 IMPACT CREATION PHASES

We broke down the core structure of the envisaged plan into three stages.

Stage 1 – Awareness creation and communication foundation (M01-M06)

In the initial stage of the project, a design of a dissemination and communication strategy and plan, including a refinement of target groups and a selection of dedicated communication tools, and community building activities will take place. This will be done to set clear coordination modality with the NGI Outreach Office and to inform all relevant stakeholders about the NGI Commons scope and objectives. During this phase, WP4 will also support all other NGI Commons WPs in the creation of liaisons and interactions with experts, relevant initiatives and organisations within the NGI ecosystem, DC/IC and OS contexts, by helping to elaborate dedicated messages, news and presentations. Other activities planned for the first two quarters of the project include the creation and launch of the NGI Commons website, development of a dedicated calendar of events, production of a project introduction flyer and the general project presentation (slides), publication of first news items, regular meetings with the NGI Outreach Office, and coordination with other NGI RIAs and NGI Pilots that started at the same as NGI Commons. Participation in at least one event to present the NGI Commons goals has also been planned for that period.

Stage 2 – Community outreach and engagement (M07-M18)

Once the communication foundation has been built (impact creation strategy well defined, project website and social media launched, relevant stakeholders informed about the start and goals of the project, general project presentation and first flyer produced), we will begin to actively reach out to the main target stakeholders to gather input and generate interest in NGI

Commons, intensifying communication, dissemination, clustering/community building and engagement activities, as well as support and/or lead in organisation of events. Based on close collaboration with all project WPs, various contents will be produced to engage target stakeholders in planned activities. Key tools and activities planned for this phase of the project include: presentations, video interviews, animation of social media channels, news/blogs items pushed out via the NGI Commons website and social media, participation in strategic events to promote the results of the consultation and mapping activities, dissemination of the policy mapping report and of the IC priorities, organisation of various webinars/workshops/panels, and of the first NGI Policy Summit.

Stage 3 – Extended outreach and long-lasting impact (M18-M34)

In the last phase of the project, we will actively promote the project’s work and main achievements to extend the outreach of NGI Commons and of the overall NGI initiative to relevant DC/IC communities, policy making bodies, and relevant initiatives across Europe and beyond. During this phase, the consortium will also engage target stakeholders in providing input, validating, refining and/or formulating insights and recommendations for exploitation, sustainability and strategic long-term plans (e.g., injecting into the strategic roadmap and governance models for future commons produced by WP3). Key tools and activities planned for this phase of the project include: active communication, dissemination and production of promotional material in various forms (presentations, interviews, videos, flyers, etc.), publications, further leveraging the established liaisons with relevant initiatives, publishing news and blog items, social media presence, organising dedicated webinars, participation to events, including the second edition of the NGI Policy Summit. In this final phase, NGI Commons will also provide guidelines, which will ground the creation of an action plan for exploitation of valuable assets and the development of sustainable collaborations.

FIGURE 1: NGI COMMONS COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION PHASES

2.3 COMMUNITY BUILDING

2.3.1 Project stakeholders and key messages

One of the first tasks performed by the NGI Commons consortium was the identification and mapping of relevant stakeholders. This exercise of positioning the NGI Commons stakeholders on the stakeholder map presented in Figure 2 helped us visualise the relationships with target

groups to understand who has interest in or influence over the project and can therefore contribute to its development.

FIGURE 2: MAP OF NGI COMMONS RELEVANT STAKEHOLDERS

The x-axis represents a stakeholder’s level of power or influence over the project while the y-axis indicates their level of interest in the project. A stakeholder’s position on the map determines how the consortium will engage with them, including the intensity and frequency of engagement. Periodically reevaluating, and, if needed, remapping the NGI Commons stakeholders will allow us to alter our messages and engagement strategies.

The identification and mapping of relevant stakeholders will support the project success in several ways:

- By identifying relevant individuals, groups, or organisations that might impact or be impacted by the project, we make sure that no important group is overlooked.
- By classifying stakeholders based on their influence and interest, we can prioritise our engagement efforts to focus on those who have the most significant impact on the project or those who are most affected by project work and results.
- Understanding stakeholders’ positions and interests makes it easier to craft personalised communication strategies to ensure the right message reaches the right groups.
- By identifying potential areas of concern, resistance, or opposition early on, we will be able to anticipate and address potential challenges proactively, before they become project risks.

The most relevant project stakeholders, their position on the stakeholder map, and the respective engagement strategies for each target group are described below.

2.3.1.1 Digital/internet commons community

One of the primary target stakeholder groups NGI Commons plans to reach includes digital/internet commons communities, practitioners, organisations, and experts, such as European Wikimedia Chapters, Wikimedia Foundation, Creative Commons, Open Knowledge Foundation, Commons Network, and other local groups working on initiatives strengthening digital public spaces.

The measures to engage with this group of stakeholders will include stakeholder consultations and workshops and identification of key actors and groups for inclusion in DCTF and SAP contributions to key events of the above communities. The interest of this target group lies in the fact that NGI Commons develops a strategic approach towards building public digital infrastructures that provide an infrastructure for digital commons initiatives, further amplifying their impact. NGI resources (community services and funding) can help grow digital/internet commons, while increasing their visibility and building a common understanding of their relevance. In reference to the stakeholder map presented in Figure 2, this group of stakeholders will be managed closely.

2.3.1.2 Open source community

NGI Commons aims to support the growth of open source, open hardware and open standard communities by analysing their needs, promoting their efforts, facilitating access to funding and accounting for their needs at policy level.

The project will engage with open source, open hardware and open standards experts, foundations, and communities through DCTF, workshops, expert sessions, events, such as LF events, CHAOSScon, FOSDEM, Open Source Experience and via active participation in communities, such as OSPO++, TODO group, and Cyber Statecraft Initiative. In reference to the stakeholder map presented in Figure 2, this group of stakeholders will be managed closely.

2.3.1.3 Extended NGI community

The extended NGI community includes:

- **11 ongoing NGI RIAs and the NGI FUND.**

Reasons behind their interests: NGI Commons helps promote Open Calls and other activities pursued by the NGI RIAs towards DC/IC/OS/OH initiatives and communities; NGI Commons helps assess the leverage impact of NGI funding/resources; NGI Commons helps identify DC/IC priorities for new/future Open Calls.

Planned engagement measures: NGI Comm Task Force, NGI Working Groups, workshops, regular and dedicated NGI calls/meetings

- **NGI Third Party beneficiaries/Innovators/SMEs/Startups**

Reasons behind their interests: NGI offers equity free funding to innovators at work to develop an internet of trust; NGI Commons helps DC/IC/OS/OH innovators to connect and access NGI resources to accelerate their efforts.

Planned engagement measures: News/blog items/newsletter, social media, NGI.eu portal, workshops, events, e.g., FOSDEM, APELL, liaisons with Digital SME Alliance and relevant Digital Innovation Hubs.

- **NGI Pilots, and, indirectly, Social Science and Humanity experts and user organisations**

Reasons behind their interests: DC/IC/OS/OH efforts are essential for a democratic and autonomous digital transformation of the economy; DC/IC communities can help accelerate the adoption and further development of NGI solutions across various sectors; NGI Policy efforts are key to ensure further investments.

Planned engagement measures: NGI Comm Task Force, NGI Working Groups, workshops, regular and dedicated NGI calls/meetings

The stakeholders within the extended NGI community have been placed on the “keep informed” square on the stakeholder map presented in Figure 2.

2.3.1.4 Policymakers

As NGI Commons supports the implementation of digital sovereignty principles through connecting the bottom-up initiatives with the larger policy landscape, policymakers, regulators, legislators, and funders (including GovStack, Sovereign Tech Fund, DPGA, OSOR, EC OSPO network, ECCC, ISC, EIT Digital, future Interoperable Europe Community, EDIHs, TTCs, etc.) are among its key stakeholders.

The project plans to engage this group via interviews, ad hoc contact points, expert sessions, webinars, and events, such as the NGI Policy Summit, EU Open Source Policy Summit, Digital Assembly, IGF, etc. This group of stakeholders has been placed on the “meet their needs” square on the stakeholder map presented in Figure 2.

2.3.1.5 Researchers

The following research groups and scientific associations will receive submissions and/or information on the project’s results:

- ISOC (Internet society)
- GIGANET (Global Internet Governance Academic Network)
- IASC (International Association on the Study of the Commons)
- IAMCR (International Association of Media and Communications Research)
- The global Network of Internet & Society Centers (NoC) and its European hub
- ECREA (European *Communication Research and Education Association*)
- Gikll – Geek Law conference
- Tilburg Institute for Law, Technology, and Society (TILT) conference
- European Association for the Study of Science and Technology (EASST)
- Society for the Social Studies of Science (4S)
- Association of Internet Researchers (AoIR)

In addition to these yearly conferences and academic associations for research in media and communications, internet law, science and technology studies, and internet science, specific calls related to DC/IC, from smaller events or other research communities, will be monitored and targeted.

This group of stakeholders has been placed on the “keep informed” square on the stakeholder map presented in Figure 2.

2.3.1.6 Civil society beyond digital/internet commons communities

This group of stakeholders includes the organisations from the EDRI Network, SOMO, and Access Now, among others. The interest of civil society organisations beyond digital/internet commons communities in the NGI Commons project lies in (1) NGI’s human-centric and ethical solutions, which can empower end users, as well as public and private organisations, and (2) in the fact that DC/IC efforts and the NGI resources have great potential for alternative digital social innovation. The planned engagement measures include the identification and engagement with relevant NGOs, Charity Foundations, Think-Tanks and Associations, Groups and Networks, Social and Solidarity economy companies and entrepreneurs via the project website, social media and events. This group of stakeholders has been placed on the “keep into account” square on the stakeholder map presented in Figure 2.

2.3.2 Liaisons and synergies

2.3.2.1 Liaisons within the NGI

NGI Commons recognises the importance of establishing and maintaining strategic liaisons within the NGI ecosystem. These collaborations are essential for exchanging knowledge, aligning efforts, and amplifying the impact of initiatives aimed at shaping a more inclusive, resilient, and sustainable digital future for Europe.

Liaisons within the NGI ecosystem serve multiple strategic purposes, including:

- **Enhancing synergy:** By aligning activities and objectives across projects, we ensure that efforts are complementary and mutually reinforcing, thereby maximising the collective impact.
- **Knowledge sharing:** Collaborations facilitate the exchange of insights, best practices, and lessons learned, fostering innovation and efficiency across projects.
- **Resource optimisation:** Through shared initiatives and resources, projects can achieve more with less, avoiding duplication and leveraging collective strengths.
- **Community building:** Engaging with a broader network of stakeholders strengthens the NGI community, promoting a cohesive vision and wider adoption of NGI principles.

NGI Commons actively seeks to establish liaisons within the NGI ecosystem:

- **NGI Communications Task Force:** As a central hub for NGI's communication efforts, collaboration with the Task Force ensures that messaging is coherent, strategic, and impactful.
- **NGI Projects:** Direct engagement with other NGI projects, including both Research and Innovation Actions (RIAs) and Coordination and Support Actions (CSAs), fosters collaborative efforts in research, innovation, and community engagement.
- **European Commission (EC):** Liaising with the EC enables alignment with policy objectives, ensuring that the project contributes to Europe's strategic digital goals.

NGI Commons employs several approaches to foster effective liaisons:

- **Regular coordination meetings:** Scheduled meetings with key partners facilitate ongoing dialogue, coordination of activities, and identification of collaboration opportunities.
- **Joint initiatives:** The project seeks to co-create events, campaigns, and resources with partners, leveraging collective expertise and networks.
- **Knowledge exchange platforms:** Utilizing online platforms and forums for knowledge sharing allows partners to access and contribute to a rich repository of insights and resources.

2.3.2.2 Liaisons with the NGI Outreach Office

The NGI Outreach Office (NOO) plays a crucial role in the NGI ecosystem by coordinating communication and marketing efforts, engaging stakeholders, and disseminating the results and innovations developed within the NGI initiative. The knowledge and insights gathered by the NGI Outreach Office is very important for NGI Commons in several ways:

1. **Dissemination:** The NOO has effective channels and tools for disseminating project results. NGI Commons can use these channels to promote its outcomes, ensuring that the project's contributions to the NGI ecosystem are visible. This includes leveraging the NGI website, social media platforms, newsletters, and events.
2. **Collaborations:** The NOO's knowledge of the NGI landscape can facilitate the identification of synergies and potential collaborations with other NGI projects and initiatives. This can lead to joint activities, shared resources, and cooperative efforts that amplify the impact of NGI Commons and contribute to the overall goals of the NGI initiative.
3. **Best practices:** The accumulated experience of the NOO in engaging with the NGI community provides a wealth of best practices and lessons learned. NGI Commons adopt proven strategies for community engagement, event organisation, and communication.
4. **Policy impact:** The NOO's interactions with European Commission policymakers offer insights into the policy impact strategies. NGI Commons can use this knowledge to align its activities with EU policy objectives, engage in policy dialogues, and contribute to shaping policies that support the NGI vision.

2.3.2.3 Liaisons and collaboration with other initiatives

Liaisons with EDIC

The consortium partners are in frequent contact with the representatives of the EDIC working group in order to exchange information, align, and find activities of mutual interest that may benefit the development of both initiatives.

The NGI Commons consortium will also liaise with:

TABLE 1: LIAISONS AND COLLABORATION WITH OTHER INITIATIVES

Organisation	Description	Benefits for NGI Commons
Open Source Observatory	A European Commission initiative that monitors and promotes the adoption of open source projects within public sectors across Europe.	Access to policy recommendations, best practices, and case studies related to open source in the public sector.
Centre for Digital Sovereignty	Focuses on enhancing the digital autonomy of nations or regions by ensuring control over their data and digital infrastructures.	Insights into strategies for achieving digital sovereignty and potential collaboration on digital policy initiatives.
Digital Public Goods Alliance	A multi-stakeholder initiative aimed at facilitating the discovery, development, use of, and investment in digital public goods to create a more equitable world.	Opportunities to collaborate on projects that are recognized as digital public goods and to share resources.
DIAL Open Source Center	Supports the sustainable and community-driven development of open-source software for social good.	Support and resources for the development, maintenance, and scalability of open-source projects.
Open Government Partnership	Brings together government reformers and civil society leaders to create action plans that make governments more inclusive, responsive, and accountable.	Opportunities to engage in initiatives that enhance government transparency and citizen participation.

Open Data Institute	Works with companies and governments to build an open, trustworthy data ecosystem.	Expertise and support in data sharing, open data practices, and data ethics.
Open Knowledge Foundation	A global non-profit network that advocates for open knowledge, including open data and content.	Access to a broad network of open knowledge practitioners and resources for open data projects.
Commons Network	Advocates for policies and practices that foster a more equitable and inclusive Commons in Europe and beyond.	Insights and collaboration on policies that promote the Commons.
GovStack	An initiative aimed at building a stack of interoperable digital public goods, making it easier for governments to implement digital services.	Access to digital tools and best practices for developing interoperable government services.
Apache Foundation	Provides support for the Apache community of open-source software projects.	Access to a large developer community.
Creative Commons	A non-profit organization that enables the sharing and use of creativity and knowledge through free legal tools.	Resources and legal frameworks for sharing digital content under open licenses.
Open Source Initiative (OSI)	A global non-profit that advocates for open source software and certifies open source licenses.	Networking with the global open source community.
Digital Freedom Foundation	Dedicated to giving all people equal access to technology and information as well as promoting digital rights.	Support for initiatives that ensure digital freedom and rights, aligning with ethical and inclusive technology use.
Open Research Europe	A platform for the publication of research across all scientific disciplines, enabling rapid and open access to research outputs funded by Horizon 2020 and Horizon Europe.	Opportunities for disseminating research findings openly and engaging with a wide academic and scientific audience.

2.4 COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION

2.4.1 Visual identity

Visual identity consists of visible assets, such as logo, colour palette, and typography that are created to portray a certain image and distinguish the brand. It defines how those who come in contact with the brand perceive it and influences their opinion about it. Good visual identity provides unique and memorable assets and a unified and consistent 'look and feel' across all outlets (electronic and printed visual media). Several assets have been developed as part of the NGI Commons visual identity. The full Brand Guidelines can be found in ANNEX 1.

2.4.1.1 Colour palette

There is no doubt that first impressions count. The main reason why they are so important is that they last well beyond the first time we come in contact with something new. This is due to the primacy effect, which is the tendency to remember the first things in a sequence best. The

term, coined by Hermann Ebbinghaus, refers to the finding that the recall accuracy varies as a function of an item's position within a study list. It is natural for humans to make quick judgments on a subconscious level based on what they see, hear, and sense; ergo, creating a positive visual impact is vital to making a good first impression.

Having this in mind, the creative team leveraged the findings of colour psychology and colour theory and started with a foundational element of any brand identity – colour, as this is usually the first thing stakeholders see. To determine the palette that works best for NGI Commons, the team looked at the emotional associations of colours to clearly convey the NGI Commons brand personality. When choosing the colours, it was also important that they worked together in harmony, which is why the team opted for an analogous brand colour palette. Blue was picked because of its associations with technology, intelligence, and trustworthiness while purple was selected because it is associated with innovation, creativity, and ambition.

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FIGURE 3: COLOUR PALETTE FOR NGI COMMONS

2.4.1.2 Typography and logo

Like all other NGI projects, NGI Commons uses the Montserrat font, which has been modified by rounding the angles to make the NGI logos more unique. The project logo, the baseline, and the name of the sub-groups were built with this typography following the broader NGI standard, with the NGI Commons brand colours being the only distinction.

FIGURE 4: NGI COMMONS LOGO

2.4.1.3 Templates for deliverables and presentations

A Word document template was created to ensure that all deliverables produced within the scope of the project follow the same structure. The template will be used by all project partners to guarantee visual consistency of the layout, format, and boilerplate text across all documents. The document at hand also follows the defined template. In addition, a PowerPoint presentation template has been created to be used by all partners when preparing their presentations for external events, meetings, etc.

2.4.2 Project website

The NGI Commons website (see Figure 5) was developed to act as an information hub presenting the project’s goals, activities, and achievements. It features the following content:

- General information about the project, its vision, and objectives,
- A brief introduction to the members of the consortium,
- News items and newsflashes,
- A library of resources, such as public deliverables, scientific publications, videos, and presentations,
- Information on upcoming events that are relevant to the project,
- Contact information,
- The funding acknowledgment and references to the funding bodies (the European Commission and the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation).

The website was developed with the users’ needs in mind. It features a light and responsive design and a keyboard navigation bar.

FIGURE 5: NGI COMMONS WEBSITE

As one of the main dynamic dissemination channels, the website will undergo major streamlining, and it will be continuously updated throughout the lifespan of the project. Since its inception, the team is working on supporting the traffic to the website through:

- **SEO** – the website traffic will increase progressively throughout the project thanks to the implementation of techniques oriented at driving organic traffic, such as the use of targeted keywords and the production of engaging and shareable content.
- **Link building** – synergies between the project’s website and the project partners’ websites will be created, encouraging the exchange of links.

All the information and email addresses collected by the project are protected under the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). The project will only contact the people who have submitted their inquiries and send newsflashes only to those who have explicitly requested to receive them. Any person who has subscribed will be allowed to remove their email address from the list upon request. Additionally, the website provides information on the stored data and how they are used in alignment with the GDPR under the Privacy policy link (footer of the webpage).

2.4.3 Social media channels

NGI Commons will utilise various social media outlets to increase the project’s visibility, build awareness about the importance of digital commons, and advertise relevant events to support the creation of a community (and further growth of the NGI community) and redirect audiences to the project website where they will be able to find more information.

Moving away from X (formerly, Twitter), the project will use the following social media outlets:

- LinkedIn
- Mastodon
- YouTube (*with the opening of a PeerTube account in the future*)

FIGURE 6: NGI COMMONS SOCIAL MEDIA CHANNELS

The team will develop tailored banners, illustrations, GIFs, and different types of graphics to increase the attractiveness of the posts and catch the audience’s attention. All visuals used on social media will be developed in line with the NGI Commons brand identity to ensure consistency across all project channels.

NGI Commons will engage relevant organisations and initiatives to maximise the outreach through content cross-sharing and cross-posting and engagement in discussions on topics related to digital/internet commons, open-source, and the overall NGI effort.

Social Media statistics will be closely and regularly monitored and analysed to identify any need for improvement or adjustment (e.g., for a specific target group).

Table 2 presents NGI Commons partners' social media accounts that will be mentioned in relevant project posts to maximise outreach.

TABLE 2: NGI COMMONS PARTNERS' SOCIAL MEDIA ACCOUNTS

Partner	Twitter	Linkedin	Accounts on other networks
Martel	@martel_innovate	https://www.linkedin.com/company/martel-gmbh/	https://eupolicy.social/@martelinnovate
OpenForum Europe	@OpenForumEurope	https://www.linkedin.com/company/openforum-europe?originalSubdomain=be	https://mastodon.cloud/@OpenForumEurope
CNRS Center for Internet and Society	@cis_cnrs		
Open Future	@openfuture	https://www.linkedin.com/company/open-future-foundation/	https://eupolicy.social/@openfuture
Linux Foundation Europe	@LF_Europe @linuxfoundation	https://www.linkedin.com/showcase/linux-foundation-europe/ https://www.linkedin.com/company/the-linux-foundation/	https://social.lfx.dev/@linuxfoundation

2.4.4 News and press releases

NGI Commons will be publishing regular news items with updates about the project. The news items will be written in an easy-to-understand language to ensure their accessibility to a wide group of stakeholders, including the general public. They will be published on the news section of the project website and further promoted via the NGI Commons social media channels. Press releases will be published coinciding with key activities and achievements of the project (e.g., kick-off, key milestones and developments). They will be distributed to various European media outlets to raise awareness and inform the readers about the project progress and its achievements. The first press release with information about the project kick-off meeting was published on January 18, 2024 and it is available on the project website. The project will also produce white papers and policy briefs, which will be widely promoted via NGI Commons social media and available on the project website.

FIGURE 7: THE NGI COMMONS KICKOFF MEETING PRESS RELEASE

2.4.5 Newsletter and newsflashes

Regular updates on the project's activities will be injected into the NGI newsletter, while shorter NGI Commons-branded newsflashes will be issued on an ad-hoc basis, promoting highlights and disseminating announcements of relevance in an ecosystem-wide perspective. The project plans to issue at least eight newsflashes throughout its lifespan.

The design of each newsflash will be aligned with the NGI Commons brand identity. The newsflashes will be fully responsive to ensure its full readability on any device. The technology behind the newsflash will provide enough flexibility to be adapted to the communication needs of the project. All issued newsflashes will be uploaded on the project website.

A mailing list based on subscription has been created, giving the possibility to share the newsflashes via mass mailing. A registration functionality allowing interested visitors to subscribe is already available on the project website. Martel will ensure that the above mentioned actions comply with the requirements of the GDPR.

2.4.6 Other tools

To support the achievement of NGI Commons' impact creation goals, the consortium put in place several tools including Prowly (media database), Meltwater (for media monitoring), Buffer (for social media management), Tito (GDPR compliant, EU-based event management platform), and MailerLite (GDPR compliant, EU-based newsletter tool), and a premium quality hosting infrastructure for the project website.

2.4.7 Promotional material

NGI Commons will produce a variety of dedicated promotional materials presenting the project and its achievements, e.g., slide-based presentations, multimedia content, videos, flyers/brochures, posters, roll-ups, and giveaways. All materials will be developed in alignment with the planning for presentations and events and adapted in relation to specific target groups and types of events.

2.4.8 Events

2.4.8.1 Event attendance

NGI Commons anticipates frequent and active participation in events, which will serve several critical purposes, all aiming to enhance the project's impact, visibility, and collaborative potential. Each event participation will serve as a strategic step in achieving the project's overall objectives.

- Promotion and visibility: Event attendance will allow the project to showcase its work, progress, and results, leading to an increased recognition and interest of its target audiences.
- Networking and collaboration: Events bring together diverse groups of individuals and organisations. For NGI Commons, these will provide excellent networking opportunities, potentially leading to collaborations that can enrich the project and extend its impact.
- Engagement and dialogue: By participating in events, NGI Commons will foster a dialogue with target stakeholders, beneficiaries, and the public. This interaction will deepen the understanding of the project's relevance and potential impact, encouraging broader stakeholder engagement and support.

- Dissemination of findings: Through presentations and discussions, NGI Commons will be able to disseminate its findings to a broader audience, populating the knowledge base of the field and promoting sustainability of its outcomes.
- Knowledge exchange: events serve as a great platform for knowledge and insights exchange with experts, peers, and other project stakeholders. These exchanges can benefit the project, enriching its work and results. Feedback received during events can provide invaluable insights for improving the project. Whether it comes from peer discussions or formal reviews, feedback can lead to beneficial adaptations and enhancements during the project's subsequent stages.

The project consortium has already identified key events (Table 3), which will be attended to promote the project, grow awareness about its potential, and attract further stakeholders.

TABLE 3: LIST OF TARGETED RECURRING EVENTS

List of targeted recurring events (in alphabetical order)
EU Open Source Policy Summit; FOSDEM; The State of the Open Conference; Open Source Community Annual Conference; PublicSpaces Conference; Linux Foundation Open Source Summit Europe; Tallinn Digital Summit; European Digital Summit; e-Governance Conference 2024; DPGA Annual Members Meeting; OW2 Con; Open Source Summit Europe; DCPC/CIS Policy Lab; re:publica; EDRI Summit; Creative Commons Summit; Wikimania; Vivatech; Public Domain Day; csv.conf.

Independent conferences: T-DOSE (NL), Open Fest (Bulgaria), Chemnitz Linux Days (Germany), FOSSCOMM, Free and Open Source Software Communities Meeting (Greece), FOSS Conference (Germany), TuxCon (Bulgaria), DORS/CLUC (Croatia), foss-north (Sweden), Open Source Day (Poland).

Conferences backed by larger OS entities/OS project specific conferences: Open Source Summit and Embedded Linux Conference (LF), Community Over Code (Apache), DEVCONF (Red Hat), Open Source Community Annual, Conference (OW2), GopherCon Europe (Go), OWASP Global AppSec, PyCon (Python), EuroBSDCon (BSD), MozFest (Mozilla), NixCon (Nix), KiCon Europe (KiCad), COOL Days (Collabora)

National OS events: OpenExpo, Open Source Experience, State of Open Conference.

International OS events:

- Independent conferences, non-EU:
 - <https://fossasia.org/> (Asia)
 - <https://coscup.org/> (Taiwan)

Topical events: KubeCon EU, OpenCode eXperience, SFSCON, FOSS Backstage, EuroPython.

The consortium also plans to attend ad hoc events that are relevant to: EU digital policy; open source, NGI; Digital Public Spaces; AI and Commons; Open Internet and Interoperability; digital government; DPGs/DPI.

2.4.8.2 Events attended in the first six months of the project

At the time of writing (M3), the consortium members have already participated in several relevant events, namely:

- **NGI Panel: Communities, Digital Rights & The Future of the Internet:**
<https://commons.ngi.eu/2024/02/15/ngi-panel-digital-rights/>

- **Workshop on Open Source Key Areas for Digital Autonomy:** <https://commons.ngi.eu/2024/03/11/ngi-commons-and-the-world-of-open-source/>
- **The EU Open Source Policy Summit 2024:** <https://commons.ngi.eu/2024/03/11/ngi-commons-and-the-world-of-open-source/>
- **FOSDEM 2024**
- **FOSS BACKSTAGE 2024.** Mirko Boehm from Linux Foundation have a talk in the session on EU cybersecurity regulation and Open Source governance: <https://24.foss-backstage.de/sessions/?id=SVRP9E>. The video is available here: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=tHCvZD649KU&list=PLq-odUc2x7i-ww77dGasjo-d54ohCAb8k&index=11>
- **NGI Coordinators Meeting, 25-26 March, Brussels.**

FIGURE 8: SNAPSHOTS FROM THE EU OPEN SOURCE POLICY SUMMIT 2024

FIGURE 9: SNAPSHOTS FROM THE NGI COORDINATORS MEETING IN BRUSSELS

The reports with key takeaways from attended events are available on the project website.

The partners are now preparing to attend the following:

- **Open Source driving the EU Digital Decade** on April 4, 2024 in Brussels
- **ENISA Cybersecurity Policy Conference** on April 18, 2024 in Brussels
- **OW 24 - Open Source Community Annual Conference** on June 11-12, 2024 in Paris-Châtillon

2.4.8.3 Organization of events

In addition to participation in relevant external events, NGI Commons will organise dedicated online and offline events, such as workshops, webinars, expert panels/consultation sessions, policy debates, etc. to present achievements, promote the project's insights and pose the foundation for exploitation of project results. More specifically, NGI Commons plans to organise two annual editions of the **NGI Policy Summit** (in 2025 ~M18 and 2026 ~M34), dedicated **DC/IC Policy sessions at the Digital Assembly 2024, 2025 and 2026 editions**, and **a dedicated parallel session/workshop(s) about DC/IC/OS collocated with the NGI Forum**. While planning event organisation, the project consortium will strive to collocate the project events with relevant conferences to optimise resource consumption and maximise participation and networking opportunities.

2.4.9 Publications

Scientific articles will be submitted to journals and ad-hoc calls on the topic of DC/IC and also on broader topics (in order to reach larger, less niche and specialised audiences).

Topics may include: online communities, internet sustainability, internet governance, internet policy, internet regulation, digital sovereignty, online privacy, digital rights, peer production.

Journals may include: Internet Policy Review; tripleC: Communication, Capitalism & Critique; RESET - Social Sciences Research on the Internet; First Monday; Westminster University Press; Terminal; Réseaux; Information, Communication & Society; Journal of Information Technology & Politics; Science, Technology and Human Values; SCRIPTed: A Journal of Law, Technology and Society.

Blogs may also be targeted, such as the LSE Media Policy Project blog.

2.4.10 Partners' individual outreach plans

All NGI Commons consortium members are equally committed to promoting the project and will use their respective channels to maximise the project's communication and dissemination efforts. In this context, all partners are building their own communication plans, exploiting their unique expertise, networks, and partnerships. The engagement of all project partners will guarantee NGI Commons' wide reach and visibility.

Martel Innovate, who is coordinating the NGI4ALL.E project and directing the NGI Outreach Office since its inception, will ensure close interaction with the NGI Outreach Office. In addition, Martel will utilise several other resources to promote NGI Commons, namely:

Its company website with 7,7K visits and 25,4K pages views in 2023.

- The company social media channels: Twitter with 1,7K followers, LinkedIn with 2,3K followers, and the newsletter with over 1.6K subscribers.
- The NGI website with 27K visits and 49,6K pages views in 2023.
- The NGI social media channels: Twitter with 5K followers, LinkedIn with 2,2K followers, and the newsletter with 2.8K subscribers.

OpenForum Europe will focus on establishing coherence across the various outreach activities that the various partners do, as well as ensure use of its reputation as a neutral facilitator, through events such as the EU Open Source Policy Summit and OFA Academy Summit, to reach the open source community and lift up messaging around digital commons. OFE currently has 2.8K followers on Twitter/X, more than 2K followers on LinkedIn, and more than 2.2K subscribers to its newsletter. Its latest Open Source Policy Summit was attended by more than 200 individuals in the room and hundreds more online, with its 2025 summit promising to be even bigger and even better.

OFE will be able to highlight Digital Commons through its Open Source Community List, and will be running a new COP through an online collaboration platform that engages industry, commons initiatives, and experts (including policymakers). Furthermore, OFE has strong ties to EU policymakers but also to industry and business, as compared to other members, and will also use this reputation to ensure coherence between the digital commons and OSS communities. OFE will also seek to conduct complementary research and advocate for related ideas to NGI Commons, as well as highlight that messaging through its events, webinar, social media, newsletters, etc.

The **French National Centre for Scientific Research (CNRS)** Center for Internet and Society (CIS) will focus its outreach policy on academic publications in internet science and internet policy. Because output will contain not only scientific results, but also concrete guidelines and policy recommendations, the targeted audience will be broader than researchers, and include policy makers, regulators and digital rights organisations as leaders for advocacy.

The **Open Future Foundation** will focus its outreach to policy makers as a primary target audience. Open Future's outreach strategy is based on direct communication with policy makers and an opportunistic approach based on policy developments during the three years of the project, participating in relevant panels and events in addition to the ones identified in this plan. In addition to the outputs expected from this action, Open Future will regularly publish notes, opinions and event reports on relevant topics. Several major publications such as policy briefs and white papers will also be published by Open Future over the three years through the Open Future website, social media and newsletter, open knowledge repositories and other media partners as appropriate.

Linux Foundation Europe will utilise the company websites [Linux Foundation](#) with 1.2 million visits in 2023 and [LF Europe](#) with 16 thousand visits in 2023 and its social media channels: Twitter [Linux Foundation](#) with 535,000 followers and [LF Europe](#) with 1,000 followers; LinkedIn [Linux Foundation](#) with 300,000 followers and [LF Europe](#) with 5,000 followers.

3 IMPACT ASSESSMENT

The NGI Commons Community Building & Communication Strategy and Plan will be closely monitored during the whole life span of the project. The evaluation will be carried out by the Communication and Dissemination Manager on a regular basis (every six months) to ensure the success of outreach activities. A communication matrix and a set of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) were defined to help execute the strategy, measure its impact and conduct the most accurate assessment of the effectiveness of the project’s communication, dissemination, and community building activities.

COMMUNICATION MATRIX

TABLE 4: NGI COMMONS COMMUNICATION MATRIX

Target audience	Outreach and engagement goals	Outreach and engagement instruments	Outreach frequency
Digital/internet commons community	<p>Engage and collaborate on initiatives that strengthen digital public spaces.</p> <p>Serve as a connection between the community and the NGI.</p> <p>Raise awareness of the NGI within the digital commons community, and connect the two to increase the number of digital commons projects interested in NGI funding.</p>	<p>Project content promoted via the project website and social media channels (white papers, news items, communication campaigns); project presentations and networking at relevant events; distribution of printed promotional materials at events; invitations to participate in stakeholder consultations; invitations to project workshops and webinars;</p>	<p>Weekly animation of social media channels; news items published on the project website (at least bi-monthly).</p> <p>Frequent participation in relevant OS conferences.</p> <p>Quarterly invitations to workshops, events and webinars organised by the project.</p>
Open Source Community	<p>Serve as a connection between the OS community and the NGI.</p> <p>Raise awareness of the NGI within the OS community, and connect the two to increase the number of OS projects interested in NGI funding.</p> <p>Engage with the OS community to help understand its needs and formulate these requirements into policy building blocks.</p>	<p>Project content promoted via the project website and social media channels (white papers, news items, communication campaigns, videos); project presentations and networking at relevant events; distribution of printed promotional materials at events; invitations to participate in stakeholder consultations; invitations to project workshops and webinars; active participation in communities, such as</p>	<p>Weekly animation of social media channels; news items published on the project website (at least bi-monthly).</p> <p>Frequent participation in relevant OS conferences.</p> <p>Quarterly invitations to workshops, events and webinars organised by the project.</p>

	Create liaisons and synergies to establish sustainable cooperation.	OSPO++, TODO group, and Cyber Statecraft Initiative.	
Extended NGI community	<p>Integrate the NGI community deeper within the digital commons ecosystem.</p> <p>Engage with the NGI community to help calculate the leverage effect of NGI funding.</p> <p>Raise the NGI Community's awareness of policy developments and use its expertise in proposing policy building blocks.</p>	<p>Regular exchanges with other NGI projects during the NGI Tasks Force calls; project content promoted via the project website and social media channels (white papers, news items, communication campaigns, videos); project presentations and networking at relevant events; distribution of printed promotional materials at events;</p>	<p>Weekly animation of social media channels; news items published on the project website (at least bi-monthly).</p> <p>Monthly participation on the NGI Communication Task Force.</p> <p>Weekly coordination with the NGI Outreach Office.</p>
Polymakers	<p>Policy makers and funding authorities will be better aware of the relevance of NGI solutions and funding, as well as of the impact that the DC efforts have on a more inclusive, open, sustainable, human-centred internet, and thus will be willing to provide more funding opportunities. National and European strategic policy agendas accounting for DC/IC needs and priorities and integrating commoners policy building blocks.</p>	<p>Interviews; ad hoc contact points; expert sessions; webinars; big events, such as the NGI Policy Summit, EU Open Source Policy Summit, Digital Assembly, IGF, etc.</p>	<p>Quarterly in-person communication with key policy-makers.</p> <p>Presentations and meetings at relevant conferences.</p> <p>Ad-hoc providing input for policy initiatives.</p> <p>Regular sharing of the outcomes of research to form policy recommendations.</p>
Researchers	<p>Contribute to the sustainable growth of commons-based and open source initiatives, enabling research and scientific advances in several areas, including public digital infrastructure, sovereign, private and unbiased data, lock-in-free upskilling, cybersecurity, interoperability, digital wallets and identity and open hardware.</p>	<p>Publication of key findings and project results in high impact journals; project content promoted via the project website and social media channels (white papers, news items, communication campaigns, videos); project presentations and networking at relevant events; distribution of printed promotional materials at events;</p>	<p>Periodically sharing all research outputs on the website and in online open source based databases.</p> <p>Weekly animation of social media channels; news items published on the project website (at least bi-monthly).</p>

Civil society beyond digital/internet commons communities	Raise awareness and interest in the open source technologies and explain the importance of the EU investment into digital public goods. Ultimately increase the use of open source technologies in this community.	Project content promoted via the project website and social media channels (white papers, news items, communication campaigns, videos);	Weekly animation of social media channels; news items published on the project website (at least bi-monthly).
General public	Raise awareness about the role and importance of digital commons and the ongoing digital transformation; increase understanding of the importance and potential of Pan-European collaboration; show what the public money is invested in and why. Explain the positive effect of NGI financing.	Engaging content published on the project website and social media channels (white papers, news items, communication campaigns, videos).	Weekly animation of social media channels; news items published on the project website (at least bi-monthly).

KEY PERFORMANCE INDICATORS

TABLE 5: COMMUNICATION-RELATED KPIS

Measure	Indicators	Target	Source and methodology
Project website	N. of unique visitors per year	>2,500	Matomo analytics
Social networks	N. of followers	>1,000	Social media animation
Flyers Posters/roll ups	N. of flyers N. of posters/roll-ups	≥4	Distribution online and via attended/organised events
Publications	N. of policy briefs, reports, white papers, scientific publications	≥12	Online distribution via NGI portal / social media
News and blogs items	N. of contributions	≥24	Items published on the website and echoed across social media
Newsflashes	N. of published editions	≥8	Recording of subscribers to the electronic newsflash
Videos	Short informative video interviews (max 3min) with experts	at least 10 3 by end of Y3	Video interviews published on the NGI YouTube channel

	Promo videos about NGI/DC/IC		
NGI Policy Summit	Organisation of a yearly event focused on the Policy topic	2 annual editions > 250 participants	Attendance proof, presented material, photos, social media animation, events' reports
Participation in events and presentations	N. attended events to present NGI Commons, to reach out and engage stakeholders, to promote NGI/DC/IC	> 15 events by the end of Y3	Attendance proof, presented material, photos, social media animation, events' reports
Experts' consultation workshops	N. of workshops engaging DC/IC experts in WP1 and policy makers in WP3	≥ 2 ≥ 6	Presentations, informative and promotional material, reports
DCTF meetings	Number of meetings - bimonthly N. of experts engaged overall	~ 15 >70	Presentations, agendas, minutes, reports
Webinars on various selected topics	N. webinars N. of participants at each one	>6 >50	Presentations, agendas, minutes, reports

4 CONCLUSIONS

D4.1 Community Building & Communication Strategy and Plan was developed to provide guidelines and a consistent framework for all planned project activities to ensure NGI Commons' broad visibility, adequate promotion, and uptake of its results. The document presents the initial communication, dissemination, and community building strategy, describes various activities conducted between M1 and M3, and outlines the planned promotional activities for the coming months. Developing this strategy at the early project stage will allow NGI Commons to maximise the impact of communication, dissemination, and stakeholder engagement activities and sustain the concepts and knowledge developed throughout the project.

The goal of this plan is to guarantee that:

- all outreach activities follow the guidelines and are executed within the planned schedule,
- the messages are consistent and of a high standard,
- all consortium members contribute to promoting the project.

The consortium defined a monitoring and evaluation framework to measure the achieved progress and impact of the proposed strategy. Deliverable *D4.2 Community Building & Communication Strategy Report* due at M18 will provide more details on the progress of the strategy and the effectiveness of the performed impact creation activities.

ANNEX 1

FONT TYPES: NGI COMMONS

NGI Commons's brand uses the open source fonts from Google Fonts: Dela Gothic One for headings and Montserrat (Regular and Bold versions) for body copy and headings too. The usage of other versions of the fonts are allowed. This applies to the website, presentations, press releases and other promotional material.

For deliverables, the system font Arial (*only* Regular and Bold versions) should be used instead, to avoid missing font issues, as those documents are likely to be mainly edited outside design departments. It could be used also for presentations in case the two brand fonts are missing.

Alternative body copy and headings *(for deliverables and presentations)*

Arial regular

ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz 1234567890

Arial bold

ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz 1234567890

Headings

(website, presentations, press releases and other promo materials)

Dela Gothic One

ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
1234567890

Body copy - sometimes headings too

(website, presentations, and all promotional materials)

Montserrat regular

ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz 1234567890

Montserrat black

ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz 1234567890

FONT TYPES: NGI

The font used is Montserrat. It has been modified by rounding the angles to make the logo more human, warm and unique.

The letter "G" has also been modified so that there is no possible confusion with the letter "O". The logo, the baseline and the name of the sub-groups are built with this typography. No other font is allowed in the use of these three elements.

Original Montserrat
Modified Montserrat

The use of italics is only allowed for the writing of testimonials (quotes). Regarding the logo, this form of font should not be used.

Montserrat Light

ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
1234567890(,;:?'€&*)

Montserrat Regular

ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
1234567890(,;:?'€&*)

Montserrat Bold

ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
1234567890(,;:?'€&*)

Montserrat Black

ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
1234567890(,;:?'€&*)

CORPORATE COLORS: NGI COMMONS

A main palette of 3 colors based on the logo color scheme. These are the colors of the logo gradient and elements. In combination with the main colors palette, there are also the three main colors for NGI plus a dark purple that can be used for text (as alternative for the black color) and dark backgrounds. Greyscale colors are accepted.

For slide presentations and deliverables: the color of standard elements has been defined and locked in the respective templates, as those documents are likely to be mainly edited outside design departments. To change colors (icons or additional text), editors will find the corporate color palette in the templates.

Hexa:	#E9316F	#69529A	#009B93	#6F9AAB	#205374	#00AFBC	#271D36
RGB:	233/49/111	105/82/154	0/155/147	111/154/168	32/83/116	0/175/188	39/29/54
CMYK:	0/90/25/0	70/75/0/0	95/0/50/0	67/27/28/6	90/60/33/20	74/4/28/0	90/95/40/60

CORPORATE COLORS: NGI

The main colors of NGI's visual identity are those shown below. They can not be changed, reversed or altered. The color of the name following the logo (and the baseline "Internet of humans") is the same regardless of the logo that precedes it, as per the NGI projects.

The color gradient follows a precise axis that starts from the bottom left of the element and ends at the right-hand point of the same element. The darkest color of the gradient is always on the left. Also the NGI projects have to apply this rules in their color palette for the NGI tag.

Hexa:	#002774	#00A7E0	#007A88
RGB:	00/39/116	0/167/224	0/122/136
CMYK:	100/0/0/20	0/0/0/0	100/0/0/0

DOS AND DONT'S

Basic instructions on how to use the main logo - and its variations - over different types of backgrounds.

Do's

Negative version on high contrasted background.

Main version on background assuring high contrast.

Don'ts

Not enough contrasted background.

Not enough contrasted background.

LOGO VARIATIONS

The main logo is also provided in the variations depicted here below, to allow readability over dark backgrounds or for black and white printing purposes.

Negative version

Black&White version

LOGO: NGI COMMONS

Main and icon versions of the NGI Commons logo with some basic recommendations.

Main version

Icon version

Safe area

Minimum size

LOGO: NGI

There is no mandatory size for the use of the NGI logo. Sizes and proportions should be based on available space, aesthetics, function and readability. It is recommended that you do not use the logo version with the baseline in sizes that are too small to maintain maximum readability. The long version of the logo: Next Generation Internet can also be used in small sizes.

LOGO: NGI

There is no mandatory size for the use of the NGI logo. Sizes and proportions should be based on available space, aesthetics, function and readability. It is recommended that you do not use the logo version with the baseline in sizes that are too small to maintain maximum readability. The long version of the logo: Next Generation Internet can also be used in small sizes.

EC ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

All the EC funded projects should clearly show the acknowledgement to the EC fund in all the materials. Website and deliverables should use the long version acknowledgement (with the SERI logo), instead for dissemination & communication materials (e.g. flyers, posters, roll-ups, brochures, videos, slides etc) also the short version (with just the EU Funded logo and the NGI one) is accepted. Below there are some examples of the elements to show in different positions.

Long version (EU funded + SERI) | mandatory for deliverables and website

Funded by EU's Horizon Europe programme under Grant Agreement number 101135279 (NGI Commons). This work has received funding from the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (SERI).

Short version (EU funded + NGI) | for all the dissemination materials

Funded by EU's Horizon Europe programme under Grant Agreement number 101135279 (NGI Commons). This project is part of the NGI Initiative.

2024-2026 NGI Commons | This work is licensed under CC BY-SA 4.0

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CONTACTS

For any questions regarding the NGI Commons graphic assets and the uses you would like to make of them, do not hesitate to contact **Margherita Facca from Martel Innovate:** margherita.facca@martel-innovate.com

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Funded by EU's Horizon Europe programme under Grant Agreement number 101135279 (NGI Commons). This project is part of the NGI Initiative. This work has received funding from the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (SERI).

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